

**APPLICATION OF MULTI-ISOTOPE DATA (O, D, C and S) TO QUANTIFY
REDOX PROCESSES IN URBAN GROUNDWATER.**

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Abstract

The different recharge sources and their mixing ratios were investigated in water samples from an urban aquifer. Two distinct zones from Barcelona city were compared: (1) Poble Sec and (2) Besòs River Delta, which are located in a densely populated area with a strong industrial impact. In this study one hundred and six water samples were collected from July 2007 to May 2010 for hydrochemical and isotopic characterization. The application of environmental isotopes coupled with hydrochemistry provided the necessary information to isotopically quantify groundwater recharge sources and evaluate the occurrence of redox processes. In Besòs River Delta, a decrease in dissolved sulphate concentration and an increase in $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{SO}_4}$ values were observed in groundwater samples, both indicating sulphate reduction. Moreover, other chemical indicators supported a reducing environment, such as low or null levels of dissolved oxygen and nitrate, the presence of ammonium and an increase in dissolved iron and arsenic. The reducing conditions were probably induced by the organic carbon dissolved in water infiltrating from the River Besòs. In Poble Sec, the relationship between $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{SO}_4}$ presented a strong influence of sewage water infiltration into the aquifer. However, the aquifer is oxic and there is no influence of sulphate reduction.

Key words: environmental isotopes, urban groundwater, mixing analysis, redox processes, Barcelona.

1. INTRODUCTION

Deterioration of groundwater quality in urban aquifers has become a matter of concern. In such areas, groundwater can be contaminated by a wide range of anthropogenic pollutants. Moreover, groundwater can be an alternative source of water supply in cities with an arid to semiarid climate (Tubau *et al.*, 2010). A proper assessment of groundwater quality requires the quantification of the total recharge and the composition of the various sources involved. These quantitative assessments enable to identify the origin and the fate of pollutants (from pollution to attenuation) and also evaluate management strategies.

However, evaluating the recharge in urban environments is essentially different from rural areas. This is mainly due to the high number of different sources, their variable composition, and the geochemical processes undergone by the mixtures. Thus, many traditional mixing ratio computations require that the concentrations of end-members to be different and accurately known. Currently, the concentrations of the different species in the end-members are not usually known with certainty. They can be highly variable in space and, especially, in time. This could be the reason why studies to identify and quantify sources and processes involved in the water quality of an urban aquifer are very scarce (see Vázquez-Suñé *et al.*, 2010 and references therein, for a review).

Some common sources of groundwater in urban areas are sewer leakage and infiltration from waste water treatment plants. These sources provide organic carbon to the water and promote biodegradation reactions of a variety of pollutants (nitrate, sulphate, arsenic-bound to iron, organic micropollutants). Biodegradation processes are related to the redox state of water. Therefore, identifying the redox evolution along a flow line is a key issue.

Unlike physical processes such as dispersion, mixing and dilution; biodegradation implies a decrease in the total dissolved mass of a solute and may involve a variation of its isotopic proportions. This suggests that isotope studies can be helpful to identify and quantify biodegradation processes. In fact, the application of environmental isotopes has been employed to characterise and assess different issues in urban groundwater recharge. Butler and Verhagen (1997) used water isotopes in the study of the city of Pretoria (South Africa) to differentiate between the local water recharge and water supply, which had a different isotopic composition. Choi *et al.* (2005) complemented a hydrochemical study in the city of Seoul (South Korea) with

isotopic data (water molecules and tritium) to determine the relationship between the uses of the soil and degradation of the groundwater quality. The isotopic composition of dissolved inorganic carbon has been used to quantify the recharge in Japan (Yasura *et al.*, 1999) and to identify old landfills (Clark and Fritz, 1997). Nitrate and sulphate isotopic compositions have been used to identify the different sources of contamination in urban aquifers and geochemical processes taking place in the aquifer (Fukada *et al.*, 2004; Bottrell *et al.*, 2008; Li *et al.*, 2010; Hosono *et al.*, 2011a). However, there are few multi-isotopic studies carried out in urban areas that not only identify the recharge sources but also quantify hydrochemical processes that may affect the pollutants (Osenbrück *et al.*, 2007; Hosono *et al.*, 2009, 2010 and 2011b). To sum up, isotopes have been used successfully to identify and quantify the extent of redox processes, but in these approaches, the isotopic composition of the recharge sources was assumed constant. Furthermore, no degree of uncertainty was considered either in these sources or the observation points.

The main objective of this study was to investigate the occurrence of redox processes in an urban aquifer with environmental isotopes using mixing ratios accounting for the uncertainty of both the recharge sources and the observation points. This included the identification of the recharge sources and their isotopic composition, the evaluation of the mixing proportions for each sample, and the quantification of the geochemical processes undergone. To this end, $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, $\delta\text{D}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$, $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{SO}_4}$ and $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ coupled with hydrochemistry data were analyzed in groundwater samples collected at two different areas from the city of Barcelona from February 2007 to May 2010. Vázquez-Suñé *et al.* (2010) previously determined the different sources of urban recharge in the aquifers of Barcelona. We used a multivariate statistical analysis method using the MIX code (Carrera *et al.*, 2004) to estimate the composition of the recharge sources and quantifying the proportions in which the different sources contribute to the total groundwater recharge in a given sample.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Site description

The study area consists of two distinct zones: Poble Sec and Besòs River Delta, which are located in the Barcelona metropolitan area (NE Spain). Barcelona is bordered by the Mediterranean Sea, the Collserola range and the Rivers Besòs and Llobregat (Figure 1). Climate is typically Mediterranean with an average rainfall of 600 mm/year.

2.1.1 Previous works related to Barcelona urban groundwater

Vàzquez-Suñé *et al.* (2010) identified several recharge sources in the aquifers of Barcelona by means of end member mixing analysis. Using a large hydrochemical database, 8 different recharge sources could be identified based on 8 and 12 tracers. The recharge sources identified are the direct rainfall recharge which occurs in the non-urbanised areas in the Collserola Range. There are also three groundwater recharge sources from anthropogenic activities: (1) loss from water supply network (Barcelona is supplied with water from the Rivers Ter and Llobregat, which divide the city into two zones with a differing water quality), (2) loss from sewage water and (3) the runoff water in paved areas that washes the urban surface atmospheric deposition and recharges the aquifers through direct infiltration or sewer seepage. Finally, there are two inflows from surface water bodies: seawater intrusion and water from the heavily polluted River Besòs, which must be considered as a potential recharge sources in lower areas of the city. The latter contains a large proportion of effluents from waste water treatment plants. Tracers included chloride, sulphate, $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, $\delta\text{D}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$, boron, fluoride, bromide, zinc, total nitrogen, residual alkalinity and EDTA. Some of the tracers used appear to be non-conservative and to address this uncertainty mixing ratios were computed considering and not considering the questionably conservative species. The authors concluded that the results using 8 (chloride, sulphate, $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$, fluoride, bromide, $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, $\delta\text{D}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ and total nitrogen) and 12 species were similar in terms of mixing ratios and suggested that the results obtained with 12 species were more realistic. According to Vàzquez-Suñé *et al.* (2010), 52% of the average total recharge in Barcelona aquifers was from loss in the water supply (22%) and sewage network (30%). Runoff water had a variable but locally major impact on the water resources representing, on average, 20 %, followed by rainfall recharge in non-urbanised area (17%) and the River Besòs (11%).

Similarly, Jurado *et al.* (2012) evaluated the total recharge in three different zones of the Barcelona metropolitan area to investigate the occurrence of illicit drugs in an urban aquifer. This included the two pilot zones of Poble Sec and the Besòs River Delta. Overall, Poble Sec aquifers were mainly recharged from loss in sewage and water supply networks and the River Besòs was by far the largest contributor of the Besòs River Delta aquifers. In that work, the tracers used to evaluate the recharge sources were not specified. Other studies developed in Barcelona aquifers were concerned with the

presence of organic micropollutants such as surfactants (Tubau *et al.*, 2010) and pharmaceutical active compounds (López-Serna *et al.*, 2012).

In the present work, we have extended the previous works carried out in Barcelona aquifers by the aforementioned authors in two aspects. Firstly, in contrast to Vázquez-Suñé *et al.* (2010) who evaluated the total recharge at a regional scale, we have focused on two specific zones of the Barcelona metropolitan area: Poble Sec and Besòs River Delta. Secondly, although these two distinct zones were included in the study of Jurado *et al.* (2012), they did not use environmental isotopes to evaluate the total recharge. Moreover, in both works, the evaluation of redox processes using environmental isotopes coupled with hydrochemistry has not been performed.

2.1.2 Hydrogeology of the pilot zones

Currently, groundwater in Poble Sec and Besòs River Delta areas is only used for secondary uses such as street-cleaning and to water public gardens. But it can be considered as an option as tap water resource, especially in periods of drought, since there are several aquifers with different lithologies, characterised by their geological age, under the city (Figure 1). The Paleozoic aquifer outcrops at the topographic heights located NW, which consists of shales and granites. Quaternary and Tertiary aquifers are found in the rest of the city. From the geological point of view, Poble Sec is located in the Barcelona Plain made up of carbonated clays. Below the Quaternary, the Tertiary (Miocene) is present. Miocene is made up of sandstones, marls and sandy gravels. Besòs River Delta is located in the Quaternary Besòs Delta, which is bordered by the River Besòs and is close to the underground car park at the Plaça de la Vila site (Figure 1). The river flow is heavily dependent on seasonal rainfall. The average flow of the river is 2.5 m³/s, except for heavy rain events. Groundwater flows generally from the River Besòs to the car park since there is a continuous pumping of about 150 l/s to avoid seepage problems. The basement is made of Palaeozoic granites and Cenozoic units, which consists of Miocene matrix-rich gravels and Pliocene grey marls. The fluvio-deltaic sediments of the Besòs Delta Complex are placed on the top of this basement, including 3 aquifers composed of sandy and gravelly bodies separated by lutitic units (Velasco *et al.*, 2012).

2.2 Chemical reactions quantification.

The methodology to evaluate the occurrence of redox processes consist of: (1) identification of the potential recharge sources and selection of the appropriate tracers, (2) evaluation of the mixing ratios in groundwater recharge and composition of the sources by means of multivariate statistical analysis and (3) assessment of the fate of environmental isotopes in groundwater samples.

We used the MIX code (Carrera *et al.*, 2004) to evaluate the occurrence of redox processes. The proposed algorithm consisted of the following steps: (1) Definition of initial mixing ratios by conventional least squares, assuming that the concentrations of end-members are known; (2) given the mixing ratios, maximise the likelihood function to estimate the expected values of mixture and end-member concentrations; (3) given the expected values of mixture and end-member concentrations, maximise the likelihood to obtain the mixing ratios; (4) repeat steps 2 and 3 until convergence. A detailed description of these steps and a derivation of the necessary equations can be found in Carrera *et al.* (2004).

The MIX code can evaluate mixing ratios in cases of uncertain end-members using the concentration of mixed samples to reduce the uncertainty. Uncertainty depends on several factors. Some of these factors are (1) sampling and analytical errors in both sources and measurement points (2) the number of measured samples to accurately characterise the recharge source composition, (3) the conservative behaviour of a given tracer and (4) the occurrence of unknown processes since recharge source water entered the aquifer until the mixture. As an example, flux averaged concentrations should be used when characterising aquifer discharges to perform salt balances in rivers. However, more proportion of diluted river water could inflow into aquifers during floods. Mixing ratios are evaluated assuming that the samples are a mixture of the recharge sources in an unknown proportion. The concentration of the conservative tracers in a mixture is obtained by a linear combination of the recharge sources. But, when deviations from perfect mixture exist they may be due to chemical processes. This code was used in previous works to study the influence of mixing processes on the hydrochemical behaviour of a river (Cánovas *et al.*, 2012) and to quantify the proportions in which different sources contribute to aquifer recharge in urban areas (Vàxquez-Suñé *et al.*, 2010; Jurado *et al.*, 2012).

2.3 Sampling and analytical methods

2.3.1 Sampling

One hundred and six water samples were collected from July 2007 to May 2010 during four different field campaigns in July 2007 (c1), February 2008 (c2), October 2008 (c3) and May 2010 (c4). Four samples were from the River Besòs. One hundred and two samples were collected from groundwater: 67 from observation piezometers and 35 from pumping wells. Data of environmental isotopes $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, $\delta\text{D}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{SO}_4}$ were available for c2 to c4 and $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ only for c4. The location of the wells and the piezometers and the screen depths are displayed in Figure 1. The specific depth of the observation points is shown in Table S1 (see supplementary material for details). All the groundwater samples were obtained by pumping until a volume that was at least three times what the piezometer was extracted. Field parameters measured in situ included electrical conductivity, pH, temperature and dissolved oxygen. They were measured continuously using a flow cell to avoid contact with the air. The instruments were calibrated daily by means of standard solutions. Samples were collected after stabilization of field parameters and were not filtered in the field. They were stored in a field refrigerator and taken to the laboratory at the end of the sampling day.

2.3.2 Analytical methods

Most species were analyzed at the laboratory of the ATLL (Aigües Ter Llobregat) in Barcelona. Chloride and sulphate were analyzed using ionic chromatography (IC). Basic cations and trace metals were analyzed by ICP-MS. For As and Fe prior to the analysis; the solution was acidified with 1% (v/v) HNO_3 and centrifuged to 3500 rpm. Ammonium was analyzed by spectrophotometry (based on indophenol blue method) and a commercial reactive kit. Bicarbonate was analyzed manually by chemical evaluation with sulphuric acid, accounting for the pH of the sample. Both bicarbonate and ammonium must be analyzed within 24 hours of the sample collection.

$\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and δD of water samples were analyzed based on Wavelength Scanned Cavity Ringdown Spectroscopy (WS-CRDS) for isotopic water measurements with a L2120-i Picarro® equipment from Malaga University (Spain). Six replicates for each sample were made, although the last three were selected for statistical treatment. Three water samples with known $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and δD were used as Internal standards of NEU (-11.58,-79.48), SLAP (-6.55,-42.49) and MAR (-0.77, 0.43).

Dissolved sulphate isotopes were analyzed for $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ at the laboratory of “*Mineralogia Aplicada i Medi Ambient*” of the research group at the University of

Barcelona (Spain). The water sample was acidified with HCl and a barium chloride solution was added in excess to variable sample volume for precipitating an expected amount of around 50 mg of BaSO₄. The precipitation was held at ~100°C in order to prevent BaCO₃ formation. The hot solution rested 1-3 days to settle the precipitate that was filtered through a 3 µm paper filter, dried at room temperature (7-10 days) and inserted into a Schott glass vial. δ³⁴S of dissolved sulphate was analyzed in a Carlo Erba Elemental Analyzer (EA) coupled in continuous flow to a Finnigan Delta C IRMS. δ¹⁸O of dissolved sulphate was analyzed in duplicate using a ThermoQuest TC/EA unit (high temperature conversion elemental analyzer) with a Finnigan Matt Delta C IRMS. Isotope ratios were calculated using both international and internal laboratory standards. Dissolved inorganic carbon DIC measurements were carried out using a gas-bench system according to the use of the conventional H₃PO₄ method developed and described by Torres *et al.* (2005).

Notation was expressed in terms of delta (δ) per mil relative to the international standards (V-SMOW for δD, V-SMOW for δ¹⁸O, V-CDT for δ³⁴S and V-PDB for δ¹³C). Reproducibility of the samples was ±0.2 ‰ for δ³⁴S, ±0.5 ‰ for δ¹⁸O of SO₄⁻, ±0.2 ‰ for δ¹³C_{DIC}; ±0.2 ‰ for δ¹⁸O and ±0.3 ‰ for δD of water.

3. RESULTS

3.1 General hydrochemistry

The average concentrations (mg/L) and standard deviations of chloride, sulphate, bicarbonate, sodium, calcium, magnesium, nitrate, ammonium and electrical conductivity (EC) of the groundwater samples collected at each zone are summarised in Table 1.

Poble Sec

Groundwater samples of the Poble Sec zone were Cl-(HCO₃/SO₄)-Ca-(Na) type and no significant differences were observed among the different field campaigns (Table 1b). Chloride and sulphate levels were usually above 290 mg/L and the average electrical conductivity (EC) was 1900 µS/cm. Some redox indicators such as the high levels of dissolved oxygen and nitrate (on average 3.5 mg/L, and 93 mg/L, respectively) and the low or null levels of ammonium (on average 0.03 mg/L), evidenced the oxidising conditions of the groundwater.

Besòs River Delta

Groundwater samples of Besòs River Delta were Cl-(HCO₃)-Na-(Ca) type. The average concentration of all the species presented little variation between field campaigns c1, c2 and c3 (Table 1b). In contrast, the last field campaign c4 presented, on average, lower concentrations than the first three campaigns for all species. Among them, chloride, sodium and ammonium were the species that presented the biggest differences (Table 1b). This could be related to the geochemistry of the River Besòs since it was also Cl-Na-(Ca)-(HCO₃) type accounting for c1, c2 and c3. However, river water of the last campaign was HCO₃-Ca-(Na) type because it was collected when rain events occurred and, consequently, presented lower concentrations due to the dilution effect.

Overall, Besòs River Delta groundwater was less mineralised than Poble Sec since the average concentration of chloride, sulphate, calcium, magnesium, nitrate and EC were much lower (Table 1a). In contrast to Poble Sec, reducing conditions into groundwater were suggested by the low levels of dissolved oxygen and nitrate (on average 0.6 mg/L, and 4 mg/L, respectively) and the presence of ammonium (6.7 mg/L, on average) as well as by the characteristic sulphidic odour during sampling at the observation points located near to the river.

3.2. Environmental isotopes

3.2.1 Environmental isotopes in the recharge sources.

The isotopic composition of the recharge sources was evaluated using samples collected in different field campaigns. The isotopic composition of $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, $\delta\text{D}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{SO}_4}$ of most of the recharge sources was first analyzed between 1998 and 1999. Later, between 2006-2007 and 2008-2010, more recharge source samples were collected, including $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$. The average isotopic composition of available data and the standard deviations of the environmental isotopes $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, $\delta\text{D}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$, $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{SO}_4}$ and $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ in the groundwater recharge sources are summarised in Table 2a. We have no data of the isotopic composition for the Llobregat sewage water (SW LL) so the values were taken from Otero *et al.* (2008). The isotopic composition of the water supply is slightly lighter than the sewage water for all the isotopes (Figure 2). Sewage waters have similar isotopic composition accounting for sulphur and oxygen isotopic values of dissolved sulphate but Ter sewage water (SW T) is lighter when considering water isotopes. Significant differences also existed between Ter and Llobregat water

supply for the isotopic compositions of sulphur and oxygen isotopes of dissolved sulphate, the former being lighter (Figure 3).

3.2.2 Environmental isotopes in groundwater.

Figure 2 and Figure 3 show the values $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} - \delta\text{D}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ and $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4} - \delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{SO}_4}$ for the groundwater samples collected, respectively. Note that the isotopic composition of $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ and $\delta\text{D}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ in c4 was lighter than those measured in c2 and also c3 in both zones (Figure 2). This could be explained by the rainfall events that occurred during the c4 field campaign. In Besòs River Delta zone, rain events caused a dilution effect in the Besòs flow regime, which directly affected groundwater composition. The average isotopic values and their standard deviation of the isotopes $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, $\delta\text{D}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$, $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{SO}_4}$ and $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ measured in the groundwater samples are summarised in Table 2b for the two aforementioned zones. The results are given below.

Poble Sec

The water isotope values of the groundwater samples displayed compositional ranges between -7.3 ‰ and -5.2 ‰ for $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ and -48 ‰ and -38.5 ‰ for $\delta\text{D}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$. Notably, most of the groundwater samples display a cluster and are in accordance to the local meteoric line. Sulphur and oxygen isotope values of sulphate in groundwater varied from +7.4 ‰ to +11.5 ‰ and +8.7 ‰ and +10 ‰, respectively. The average $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ is -11.8 ‰.

Besòs River Delta

The isotopic composition of groundwater samples for $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ was similar to Poble Sec, ranging from -7.2 ‰ to -5.7 ‰ but the isotope values for $\delta\text{D}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ varied in a narrow range between -43.6 ‰ and -38.1 ‰. Regarding dissolved sulphate isotope values: $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$ ranged from +6.9 ‰ to +12.3 ‰ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{SO}_4}$ ranged from +10 ‰ to +12.5 ‰. At Besòs River Delta, the average $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ is similar to Poble Sec, being -12.4 ‰.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1 Recharge sources identification and selection of the tracers in the pilot zones

As previously mentioned, up to eight different recharge sources were identified in Barcelona urban aquifers (Vázquez-Suñé *et al.*, 2010): (1) rainfall recharge in the northern non urban area (REC), (2) river Ter water supply (TER), (3) river Llobregat water supply (LLOB) (4) river Ter sewage water (SW T), (5) river Llobregat sewage

water (SW LL), (6) city runoff (RUNOFF), (7) sea water intrusion (SEA) and (8) river Besòs (RIV). Among these recharge sources, not all were considered in the pilot zones select for this study: Poble Sec and Besòs River Delta. SEA end-member was disregarded because neither Poble Sec nor Besòs River Delta were affected by sea water intrusion. Water supply in the pilot zones comes from two different rivers: Llobregat and Ter (LLOB and TER recharge sources). Poble Sec area is supplied by the River Llobregat and Besòs River Delta area is supplied by the River Ter. Consequently, two different compositions can also be found also in wastewater. Moreover, River Besòs (RIV) presents seasonal variations which reflected changes in water quality (Vàzquez-Suñé *et al.*, 2010). Therefore, it is not sufficient to consider only one end-member from the River Besòs because aquifer samples were collected at a local level during 4 different field campaigns from 2007 to 2010. Instead, two different end-members from this river were used to account for the temporal variability: wet conditions (W) and dry conditions (D). The former corresponded to diluted water related to wet periods or water supply inputs and the latter represented concentrated waters related to dry periods.

Selecting appropriate tracers is a critical step in mixing calculations (Morris *et al.*, 2006) because ideally, tracers should be conservative and their concentrations should vary widely from one source to another. Preliminary works developed for Barcelona aquifers suggested suitable tracers for differentiating the recharge sources adequately could be chloride, sulphate, total nitrogen, $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, $\delta\text{D}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ and $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$. In this study we also included electrical conductivity, bicarbonate, $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{SO}_4}$ and $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$. We selected electrical conductivity because it behaves conservatively and the others because they may participate in the chemical reactions to be quantified. Their concentrations and isotopic compositions are detailed in Table 3a. As shown in Table 3a, tracer concentrations considering River Ter water supply and the River Besòs in wet season are similar. Consequently, we disregarded the water supply source (TER) because its contribution to the total recharge was much less significant than the River Besòs in the wet season (Jurado *et al.*, 2012). Similarly, REC was not taken into account because previous studies demonstrated its null contribution to groundwater recharge in the lower parts of the Besòs River catchment, where the samples of Besòs River Delta were collected (Vàzquez-Suñé *et al.*, 2010).

In summary, the recharge sources considered were LLOB, SW LL, REC and RUNOFF in Poble Sec zone and SW T, RUNOFF, RIV (W and T) in River Besòs Delta

zone. The tracers selected were chloride, electrical conductivity, bicarbonate, sulphate, total nitrogen, $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, $\delta\text{D}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$, $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{SO}_4}$ and $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$.

4.2. Evaluation of the mixing ratios in groundwater recharge and composition of the sources

Mixing ratios in groundwater recharge were evaluated with MIX code (Carrera *et al.*, 2004). In this code, measurement uncertainty is quantified through covariance matrices. The need to consider uncertainty in recharge source concentrations is best illustrated in Figure 4 where measured end-member concentrations fail to envelop measurements of several observation points in plots such as chloride vs. sulphate, total nitrogen, $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{SO}_4}$. The code requires defining the reliability of measurements and the results depend on the assumed standard deviations. This suggests that standard deviations should be selected carefully. The standard deviations were selected depending on whether or not the tracers were conservative. The more conservative the tracer, the lower the assigned deviation. For instance, some environmental isotopes such as $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{SO}_4}$ could be non-conservative due to chemical processes. The standard deviations assigned to the recharge sources varied from 10 % to 75 % of the concentration for a specific tracer (Table 3). In general, the standard deviations assigned were lower in groundwater samples than those assigned to the recharge sources because recharge source composition was more uncertain (Table 3b).

Once standard deviations were assigned, chemical composition of the recharge sources and mixing ratios at each observation point could be evaluated. As shown in Figure 4, computed recharge source concentrations perfectly enveloped all the computed concentrations. However, it is important to analyse, the reliability of the computed chemical composition of recharge sources. When measured and computed concentrations for all the tracers in recharge sources and observations points were compared (Figure 5), several observations could be made:

(1) Computed recharge source concentrations for chloride, sulphate, bicarbonate and electrical conductivity were similar to measured ones in both zones, falling close to the 1:1 line. The same occurred with total nitrogen in Poble Sec. Also, computed and measured concentrations at the observation points for these species fell close to 1:1 line, especially for chloride and electrical conductivity.

(2) Computed concentration of total nitrogen at Besòs River Delta for dry end-member (D) was drastically reduced. Accordingly, measured concentrations for some observation points were lower than computed ones (Figure 5b). Nitrate concentrations at River Besòs can reach levels of 15 mg/L but measured concentrations at points located near the river (SAP's and ADS6n, Figure 1) are drastically reduced to null or very low levels (on average, 0.45 mg/L). This may be indicative that denitrification could occur when river water infiltrates the aquifer. Unfortunately, we did not analyse the environmental isotopes of dissolved nitrate in groundwater.

(3) Computed recharge concentrations were in line with the standard deviations assigned (Table 4). As observed with the general hydrochemistry, the separation of the city into two distinct water quality zones was supported by the computed recharge concentrations of SW T and SW LL. Overall, sewage waters were the more mineralised waters followed by dry end-member of the River Besòs. Among them, SW LL was the recharge source with the highest levels of chloride, electrical conductivity, sulphate and total nitrogen. Conversely, wet end-member from the River Besòs presented the lowest concentrations, except for total nitrogen. A more detailed discussion of the isotopic composition of the recharge sources and the assessment of the environmental isotopes in groundwater samples can be found in the following sections 4.3 and 4.4, respectively.

Computed mixing ratios help in deriving the mass balance of the study zones and directly depend on the composition of the recharge sources. Figure 6 shows the computed mixing ratios spatial distribution at each sampling point accounted for c3 and c4 in both zones. Also, it is shown the average mixing ratios for each recharge sources considering the four sampling campaigns in both zones. According to the identified sources, in Poble Sec the average main contributor to the total recharge was sewage network loss SW LL (46%) and no significant differences were observed among the different field campaigns. Runoff water in paved areas was highly variable, ranging from 24 % to 36 % in c1 and c4, respectively. Overall, it represented the 28 % of the resident water. The remaining 26 % corresponded to water supply network loss (20 %) and the recharge in non-urbanised areas (REC, 6%). As for Besòs River Delta, RIV (River Besòs) was by far the largest contributor to the total recharge, representing 88 % in total; 60% from dry conditions and 28 % from wet conditions. Seasonal variations of River Besòs dynamics were reflected in groundwater concentrations because wet conditions end-member was represented in c4, on average, 42 % of the total recharge. This could be explained because c4 samples were collected in a rainy period. In

contrast, this end-member represented 25 %, 15 % and 29 % in the c1, c2 and c3, respectively. Table 4 shows the differences that existed between the end-members in wet and dry conditions, the latter being the one that presented high levels for all tracers, except for total nitrogen and $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$. Other contributors to the recharge were network sewage loss (SW T) and runoff water in paved areas (RUNOFF) at low percentages, representing 6 % each. Note that both SW T and RUNOFF only contributed to groundwater recharge points located close to the parking site (Figure 6).

The structure of the input file executed in the MIX code can be consulted in the supplementary material (see file *input.pdf* for details).

4.3. Isotopic composition of the recharge sources at the pilot zones.

Table 4 summarises the computed isotopic composition of the environmental isotopes at all recharge sources.

4.3.1 Isotopic composition of $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ and $\delta\text{D}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$.

The computed isotopic composition of $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ and $\delta\text{D}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ from REC presented the heaviest values among the other recharge sources. The isotopic composition of the water supply LLOB ($\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = -6.6 \text{ ‰}$ and $\delta\text{D}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = -44.3 \text{ ‰}$) shows similar values to those from the River Llobregat ($\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = -7 \text{ ‰}$ and $\delta\text{D}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = -45.5 \text{ ‰}$, Otero *et al.* (2008)). Both sewage waters (SW LL and SW T) presented similar isotopic composition. As regards to the end-members from the RIV, they presented distinct isotopic compositions. During dry conditions (D), values of $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ and $\delta\text{D}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ were heavier than those in wet conditions (W), ranging from -5.5 ‰ to -8 ‰ for $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ and from -36.7 ‰ to -47.4 ‰ for $\delta\text{D}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, respectively. This could be explained taking into consideration the variability of the rainfall in the Besòs River Delta watershed, with higher values of $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ under warm temperatures (late spring and summer). All the computed values were in line with the standard deviations assigned.

4.3.2 Isotopic composition of $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{SO}_4}$.

REC presented the lightest isotopic composition with values of $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4} = +3.1 \text{ ‰}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{SO}_4} = +6.5 \text{ ‰}$. The values of $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{SO}_4}$ and $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$ for LLOB were in agreement with reported values of the River Llobregat (Otero *et al.*, 2008). Moreover, SW LL and SW T values were in the range of the isotopic composition measured in several sewage water treatment plants located along the River Llobregat and resulted in $+7 \text{ ‰}$ to $+14 \text{ ‰}$ for $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$ and $+8 \text{ ‰}$ to $+12.5 \text{ ‰}$ for $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{SO}_4}$ (Otero *et al.*, 2008). Since the River Besòs contains a large proportion of effluents from secondary waste water treatment plants,

the isotopic composition of its dry end-member correspond to the values of sewage waters and treated sewage waters (Vitoria *et al.*, 2004 and Otero *et al.*, 2008). In contrast, wet end-member was 20% lighter than the dry end-member because of the River Besòs variability, which is controlled by rainfall.

4.3.3 Isotopic composition of $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$.

The computed values of $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ for all end-members were in complete agreement with the expected values of the $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ when the dissolved inorganic carbon of the groundwater was in equilibrium with the dioxide carbon of the soil/aquifer. These values ranged from -12 ‰ to -15 ‰ (Vogel and Ehhalt., 1963) and from -14 ‰ to -16 ‰ (Clark and Fritz, 1997).

4.4 Assessment of the fate of the environmental isotopes in groundwater samples.

Once the mixing ratios were computed and the isotopic composition in the potential recharge sources determined, it was possible to assess the fate of these isotopes in the aquifer.

Poble Sec

Figure 5a shows the measured and computed isotopic composition of $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, $\delta\text{D}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$, $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{SO}_4}$ and $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ estimated from mixing ratios. When measured and estimated values were compared, it could be seen that a great number of samples fell relatively close to the 1:1 line (ideal mixing line). This fact indicated that the isotopic values for water and sulphate isotopes could be explained by a mixing of the different recharge sources considered (REC, RUNOFF, SW LL and LLOB).

Besòs River Delta

In contrast to Poble Sec, some environmental isotopes in groundwater samples of Besòs River Delta presented different behaviour (Figure 5b). Water isotopes and $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ isotopic composition could be explained by a mixing among the recharge sources (RUNOFF, W, D and SW T). However, this could not be applied to $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{SO}_4}$ because measured values were higher than the computed ones, suggesting the occurrence of geochemical processes that depleted sulphate in groundwater. Despite dissolved sulphate behaved conservatively, the environmental isotopes of sulphate did not (Figure 5b). Therefore, groundwater samples may have shifted from their original compositions. A general trend of increasing $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$ with decreasing sulphate concentration was attributed to bacterial reduction (Grassi and Cortecchi, 2005; Yamanaka and Kumagai, 2006). The maximum extent value was 4.7 ‰ for $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$ and

2.5 ‰ for $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{SO}_4}$ (Table 5). The significance of this process and its distribution within the aquifer in terms of increments of $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$ enabled the division of this study zone according to the location of the points: (1) Points located near the river (SAP's and ADS-6n, Figure 1) and (2) points located closer to underground car park at Plaça de la Vila site (ADS-7, ADS-2, ADS-4 and ADP's, Figure 1). The observation points located close to the river, presented constant increments of $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$ during the different sampling periods (on average 2.7 ‰). But the average enrichment degree of $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$ was more important in the deeper observations points (SAP-1, SAP-2 and SAP-3) than in the shallower ones, being 3.3 ‰ and 2.2 ‰, respectively. In the rest of observation points, clearly more affected by the continuous pumping of Plaça de la Vila site, no clear tendency was observed although sulphate reduction was also occurring but to a lower degree (on average 2.1 ‰).

One of the most relevant results in this research was the quantification of sulphate reduction at each observation point (Table 5). As an example, Figure 7 shows the expected isotopic composition of $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{SO}_4}$ for c3 by simple mixing of the recharge sources (ranging between 7 ‰ and 8 ‰) and the quantification of sulphate reduction in terms of enrichment factors of $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{SO}_4}$ at each sampling point. The enrichment ratio between $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{SO}_4}$ presented a slope (m) of 2 and it was much lower than those values obtained under experimental conditions, ranging from 2.5 to 4 (Mizutani and Rafter, 1973). However, in application case studies the conditions are not as ideal as in lab experiments. The slope between $\epsilon \delta^{34}\text{S} / \epsilon \delta^{18}\text{O}$ obtained by sulphate reduction in a sandy aquifer was close to 0.70 (Strebel *et al.*, 1990). Computed values of Table 5 allowed evaluating the depleted concentration of dissolved sulphate due to sulphate reduction process. It could be quantified according to the Rayleigh fractionation equation. The sulphur enrichment factors during sulphate reduction can vary from less than 0 ‰ to more than 45‰ (Aravena and Mayer, 2010). However, they range between 10 ‰ and 20 ‰ in hydrological settings (Strebel *et al.*, 1990; Dogramaci *et al.*, 2001; Spence *et al.*, 2001). Consequently, the initial dissolved sulphate concentration ($[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]_i$) was calculated according to a $\epsilon^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4} = 20$ ‰ in groundwater samples that presented increments of $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ higher than 2 delta units in Besòs River Delta. The use of $\epsilon^{18}\text{O}_{\text{SO}_4}$ was disregarded because oxygen isotope ratios may approach to a constant value during bacterial sulphate reduction (Boettcher *et al.*, 2001). The measured values of dissolved sulphate and the isotopic composition were used as final sulphate concentration ($[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]_f$) and residual value of $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$, respectively. The initial

composition of $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$ was computed by the MIX code and this value represented a mixture among the different recharge sources. Note that the difference between residual and initial values of $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$ is the $\Delta \delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$ presented in Tables 5 and 6. Table 6 shows the evaluated initial sulphate concentration and the concentration depleted due to sulphate reduction in selected groundwater samples. Assuming that sulphate reduction occurred in the aquifer, dissolved sulphate was reduced, on average, 28 mg/L in Besòs River Delta. These concentrations were in agreement with the standard deviations assigned, representing 15% of the initial dissolved sulphate ($[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]_i$). The depleted sulphate concentration due to sulphate reduction was 18 mg/L when $\epsilon^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4} = 30 \text{ ‰}$ (see Table S2 of supplementary material).

There were other chemical indicators that supported the occurrence of the sulphate reduction process at Besòs River Delta aquifers such as the presence of ammonium, the low concentrations of dissolved oxygen and the high levels of dissolved heavy metals like arsenic (As) and iron (Fe). As shown in Figure 8, As(III) /As_T concentration ratio demonstrated that arsenic reduced form (As(III)) was the predominant dissolved specie in the observation points located close to the river (SAP's and ADS-6n, see Figure 1) and in some points located near the park site (ADPQ and ADPW, Figure 1) supporting the reducing aquifer environment. According to Pierce and Moore (1981), arsenic tends to be adsorbed by amorphous iron hydroxide because it is ubiquitous in clays, soils and sediments and might be released in groundwater where sulphate reduction can occur (Plant *et al.*, 2005).

5. CONCLUSIONS

The application of environmental isotopes coupled with hydrochemistry data using mixing ratios has provided the isotopic quantification of groundwater recharge sources and the occurrence of redox processes such as sulphate reduction. The presented approach enabled: (1) to quantify the mixing ratios into groundwater considering a degree of uncertainty in both the recharge sources and the observation points and (2) to evaluate the occurrence of redox processes at each observation point. This application has been validated into two hydrochemically distinct zones. Poble Sec, where isotopic composition of recharge sources has shown a strong influence of sewage water infiltration into the aquifers and no sulphate reduction occurred in groundwater samples. In contrast, at Besòs River Delta, mainly recharge from river Besòs water, dissolved

sulphate isotopes could not be explained by only simple mixing of the groundwater recharge sources because the measured compositions at the observation points were higher than the computed ones, suggesting the occurrence of sulphate reduction. The maximum extent value for $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$ was 4.7 ‰. The approach taken in this study can be used in other aquifer systems to quantify not only groundwater recharge sources but to also quantify processes like nitrification, denitrification, sulphate reduction and degradation of organic matter when environmental isotopic data is available.

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Figure captions.

Figure 1. On the left, schematic description of the hydrogeology of Barcelona: (1a) Llobregat Delta made up of gravels, sands, silts and clays (Holocene, Quaternary), (1b) Besòs Delta composed of gravels, sands, silts and clays (Holocene, Quaternary), (1c) Barcelona Plain consisting of carbonated clays (Pleistocene, Quaternary), (2) Barcelona Plain made up of marls, sandstones and sands (Tertiary) and (3) Collserola Range consisting of shale and granites (Palaeozoic). On the right, a piezometric map of the study area, which is divided into two distinct zones: Poble Sec (PS) and Besòs River Delta (BRD). The contour intervals are 2 m (continuous green line), for heads ranging from 5 to below 25 m (continuous blue line) and 25 m above (continuous orange line). At the bottom, observation points in each zone, including the depth of the screen: (u) upper, (m) middle, (l) lower and (a) totally screened.

Figure 2. Plot of $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}-\delta\text{D}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ accounting for the recharge sources (and standard deviation) and groundwater samples collected in both zones: Poble Sec (PS, rhombus) and Besòs River Delta (BRD, rounds). Note that the different field campaigns are represented by the shade of grey: c2 is light grey, c3 is grey and c4 is dark grey. The local meteoric line (LML) represents the monthly isotopic composition of a long-term sampling period (1985-1992) at the monitoring station of Barcelona.

Figure 3. Plot of $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}-\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{SO}_4}$ accounting for the recharge sources (and standard deviation) and groundwater samples collected in both zones: Poble Sec (PS, rhombus) and Besòs River Delta (BRD, rounds). Note that the different field campaigns are represented by the shade of grey: c2 is light grey, c3 is grey and c4 is dark grey.

Figure 4. Plots of measured and computed concentrations and isotopic compositions. Note that measured concentrations of the recharge sources fail to envelope the measured concentrations in several samples in both Poble Sec and Besòs River Delta (Chloride versus sulphate, total nitrogen, $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{SO}_4}$). Conversely, computed recharge sources perfectly encircle the computed concentrations and isotopic compositions of considered tracers. Concentrations are in mg/L and isotopic composition in ‰.

Figure 5. Computed versus measured concentrations and isotopic composition at all recharge sources and groundwater samples in Poble Sec (PS) and Besòs River Delta (BRD). Note that $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{SO}_4}$ isotopes of dissolved sulphate do not behaved conservatively at Besòs River Delta. Concentrations are in mg/L and isotopic composition in ‰.

Figure 6. Spatial distribution of mixing ratios evaluated for c3 and c4 at both zones. Note the average mixing ratios considering all sampling campaigns of each zone (PS and BRD).

Figure 7. Relationship between $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{SO}_4}$ in groundwater samples of the c3. Grey and black colours represented the observation points located near and far from the river, respectively. The encircled values are those expected by simple mixing of the recharge sources computed with MIX code. Note that the enrichment factor for $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{SO}_4}$ are detailed for each sampling point (‰).

Figure 8. On the left axis, iron and arsenic concentrations in groundwater samples collected in c4. The ratio between As (III) and the total arsenic is plotted on the right axis. The black dashed line divided Besòs River Delta study zone considering the location of the sampling points (close or far to the river, Figure 1).

TABLES

Table 1. Average concentration (mg/L) and standard deviation of selected species measured in: (1a) Poble Sec and Besòs River Delta and (1b) detailed in both zones for each sampling campaign.

Table 2. Average isotopic composition, standard deviation and number of samples of $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, $\delta\text{D}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$, $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{SO}_4}$ and $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ in **(2a)** recharge sources and **(2b)** detailed in each zone of the study area.* Values from Otero *et al.* (2008).

Table (3a) Initial concentrations of tracers selected for mixing ratios evaluation at each recharge source. The concentrations of the major ions and total nitrogen are expressed in mg/L, the electrical conductivity is expressed in $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ and the environmental isotopes in ‰. **(3b)** Standard deviations to be considered in MIX code for each tracer in the recharge sources and groundwater samples expressed as a percentage of the concentration.

Table 4. Computed concentrations and isotopic compositions in all the recharge sources for the selected tracers expressed in mg/L and ‰.

Table 5. Quantification of sulphate reduction in terms of enrichment factors of $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{SO}_4}$ (‰) at each observation point (ID) for sampling campaigns c2, c3 and c4.

Table 6. Evaluation of depleted dissolved sulphate due to the occurrence of sulphate reduction in selected groundwater samples for Besòs River Delta ($\epsilon^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4} = -20$ ‰). Note that the difference between residual and initial values of $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$ is the $\Delta \delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$ and $[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]_f$ and $[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]_i$ are the final and initial dissolved sulphate concentrations in groundwater samples.

Figures

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

Figure 3.

Figure 4.

Figure 5.

Figure 6.

Figure 7.

Figure 8.

Tables

Table 1

1a Barcelona urban groundwater

Zone	Cl ⁻	SO ₄ ²⁻	HCO ₃ ⁻	Na ⁻	Ca ²⁺	Mg ²⁺	NO ₃ ⁻	NH ₄ ⁺	EC
Poble Sec	306±30	291±49	302±35	163±33	196±26	70±14	93±29	3.2E-2±6.7E-2	1898±173
Besòs River Delta	244±35	161±14	349±31	196±29	134±9	28.5±2.5	4±7.6	6.7±3.2	1540±136

1b Detailed in both zones for each field campaign

Poble Sec									
Field campaign	Cl ⁻	SO ₄ ²⁻	HCO ₃ ⁻	Na ⁻	Ca ²⁺	Mg ²⁺	NO ₃ ⁻	NH ₄ ⁺	EC
c1	306±32	291±57	305±35	178±39	194±26	71±9.8	91±25	6E-3±2E-2	1916±219
c2	308±22	293±37	304±20	151±33	201±40	74±22.8	90±24	6.5E-2±1E-1	1899±126
c3	312±42	301±70	314±54	170±33	180±13	66±9.1	96±44	3E-2±5E-2	1900±234
c4	297±23	278±24	286±19	153±21	208±10	69±8.1	96±20	2.5E-2±3E-2	1877±100
Besòs River Delta									
Field campaign	Cl ⁻	SO ₄ ²⁻	HCO ₃ ⁻	Na ⁻	Ca ²⁺	Mg ²⁺	NO ₃ ⁻	NH ₄ ⁺	EC
c1	264±27	162±8	425±25	221±22	136±9	28.8±1.1	4.1±9.5	7.7±4.3	1612±110
c2	261±22	177±4	449±42	199±16	137±8	28.9±4.3	4.7±7.3	7.7±3	1619±83
c3	257±11	156±8	425±14	207±12	137±7	29±1.6	3.8±6.9	7.3±2.5	1580±40
c4	196±18	148±13	403±19	157±14	126±9	27.5±1.6	3.3±7.7	4.3±1.6	1356±87

Table 2**Table 2a**

Recharge sources		$\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	$\delta \text{D}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	$\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$	$\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{SO}_4}$	$\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$
Rainfall recharge in northern non urban area	(REC)	-6.4±0.3 (n=10)	-43.6±4.5 (n=10)	2.9±0.1 (n=3)	6.4±0.3 (n=2)	-13.4±1 (n=4)
Ter river water supply	(TER)	-7.3±0.3 (n=4)	-49±2 (n=4)	4.7±0.5 (n=3)	8.2±1 (n=2)	-11.7 (n=1)
Llobregat river water supply	(LLOB)	-6.9±0.3 (n=2)	-49.3±3.2 (n=2)	8.6±1.5 (n=2)	10.5 (n=1)	-
Ter sewage water	(SW T)	-6.9±0.2 (n=2)	-46.8±3.9 (n=2)	8.6±1.3 (n=4)	11.8 (n=1)	-
Llobregat sewage water	(SW LL)	-6.1* (n=1)	-39.2* (n=1)	8.7* (n=1)	10.9* (n=1)	-
City Runoff	(RUNOFF)	-5.1 (n=1)	-48 (n=1)	10.7±0.6 (n=2)	13.2 (n=1)	-
Sea water intrusion	(SEA)	1.3±0.2 (n=2)	8.4 (n=1)	20.3±0.4 (n=2)	9.8 (n=1)	-6.4 (n=1)
River Besòs	(RIV)	-6.3±0.56 (n=7)	-41±2.92 (n=7)	7.1±0.75 (n=6)	9.8±0.83 (n=5)	-12.5±2.47 (n=2)

Table 2b

Groundwater samples		$\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	$\delta \text{D}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	$\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$	$\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{SO}_4}$	$\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$
(Z1) Poble Sec	PS	-6.8±0.44 (n=39)	-44.2±2 (n=39)	9.3±0.28 (n=39)	9.8±0.75 (n=39)	-11.8±0.69 (n=13)
(Z2) Besòs River Delta	BRD	-6.38±0.40 (n=39)	-40.6±1.61 (n=39)	10.1±1.3 (n=39)	11.4±0.57 (n=39)	-12.4±0.6 (n=13)

Table 3

Table 3a											
CONCENTRATIONS (mg/L and ‰)											
Recharge sources		Cl ⁻	EC	SO ₄ ²⁻	N _{tot}	HCO ₃ ⁻	δ ¹⁸ O _{H2O}	δ D _{H2O}	δ ³⁴ S _{SO4}	δ ¹⁸ O _{SO4}	δ ¹³ C _{DIC}
Rainfall recharge in northern non urban area	(REC)	97	1000	110	2.7	280	-6.4	-43.6	2.9	6.4	-13.4
Llobregat river water supply	(LLOB)	290	1580	195	2.2	280	-6.9	-49.3	8.6	10.5	-11.7
Ter sewage water	(SW T)	347	1965	219	23.7	493	-6.9	-46.8	8.6	11.8	-14
Llobregat sewage water	(SW LL)	564	2500	336	33.8	500	-6.1	-39.2	8.7	10.9	-14
City Runoff	(RUNOFF)	88	901	101	12.5	325	-5.1	-48	10.7	13.2	-13
River Besòs (RIV)	Dry (D)	356	1997	206	10	501	-6.3	-41	7.45	9.9	-14.5
	Wet (W)	44	586	53	6.2	223	-6.3	-41	6.2	8.6	-11
Ter river water supply	(TER)	49	454	58	2	180	-7.3	-49	4.7	8.2	-11.7
Table 3b											
STANDARD DEVIATIONS (% concentration/isotopic composition)											
Recharge sources		Cl ⁻	EC	SO ₄ ²⁻	N _{tot}	HCO ₃ ⁻	δ ¹⁸ O _{H2O}	δ D _{H2O}	δ ³⁴ S _{SO4}	δ ¹⁸ O _{SO4}	δ ¹³ C _{DIC}
Rainfall recharge in northern non urban area	(REC)	20	20	20	50	25	15	15	15	15	15
Llobregat river water supply	(LLOB)	10	10	15	30	25	15	15	15	15	40
Ter and Llobregat sewage water	(SW T/SW LL)	10	10	15	30	25	15	15	15	15	40
City Runoff	(RUNOFF)	20	20	30	50	25	15	15	15	15	75
River Besòs (RIV)	(W/D)	10	10	15	15	15	20	20	15	15	30
Observation points											
(Z1) Poble Sec	PS	7.5	7.5	10	20	15	7.5	7.5	15	15	15
(Z2) Besòs River Delta	BRD	7.5	7.5	10	50	15	7.5	7.5	100	100	15

Table 4

Recharge sources		Cl ⁻	EC	SO ₄ ²⁻	HCO ₃ ⁻	N tot	δ ¹⁸ O _{H2O}	δ D _{H2O}	δ ³⁴ S _{SO4}	δ ¹⁸ O _{SO4}	δ ¹³ C _{DIC}
Recharge in northern non urban area											
River Llobregat water supply		94.8	957.9	122.7	259.9	2.7	-4.1	-35.7	3.1	6.5	-13.4
Llobregat Sewage water		320.0	1680.2	179.3	348.6	2.2	-6.6	-44.3	9.2	9.5	-11.2
Ter Sewage water		467.7	2721.5	461.4	458.9	34.2	-6.9	-43.9	9.5	8.7	-12.9
City runoff		355.4	2002.1	175.9	501.8	21.5	-6.3	-41.5	8.7	11.9	-14.7
River Besòs (RIV)		77.9	908.2	122.8	247.7	16.2	-6.9	-45.2	9.8	11.8	-10.8
Dry (D)		339.6	1981.3	208.7	516.3	2.8	-5.5	-36.7	8.0	10.4	-13.9
Wet (W)		42.1	599.4	58.8	236.7	4.1	-8.0	-47.4	6.4	8.8	-10.6

Table 5

ID	c2		c3		c4	
	$\Delta \delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$	$\Delta \delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{SO}_4}$	$\Delta \delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$	$\Delta \delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{SO}_4}$	$\Delta \delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$	$\Delta \delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{SO}_4}$
	(‰)	(‰)	(‰)	(‰)	(‰)	(‰)
SAP-4	2.4	1.9	3.1	1.6	-	0.6
SAP-3	2.7	1.2	4.2	2.5	3.5	1.5
SAP-2b	0.6	1.3	3.4	2.5	2.9	2.4
SAP-1	2.7	1.4	3.2	1.2	3.6	1.8
SAP-2	2.8	1.3	3.2	1.2	3.6	1.7
ADS-6n	1.2	0.9	3.3	1.7	3.2	2.1
ADS-7	-	0.8	3.9	1.9	-	0.8
ADPM	-	0.9	3.8	1.8	1.6	1.1
ADPW	0.9	1.4	3.7	1.4	2.8	1.3
ADPQ	1.3	1.1	3.5	1.5	2.8	1.7
ADS-2	-	-	2.6	1.0	1.2	-
ADS-4	-	-	4.7	2.1	2.3	1.1
ADPR	1.7	0.6	4.6	2.3	2.5	1.1

Table 6.

ID	$\Delta \delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{SO}_4}$ (‰)	$[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]_f$ (mg/L)	$[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]_i$ (mg/L)	$\Delta[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]$ (mg/L)
SAP-4 c2	2.4	179.9	202.5	-22.6
SAP-3 c2	2.7	178.7	204.7	-26.0
SAP-1 c2	2.7	178.6	204.3	-25.8
SAP-2 c2	2.8	177.9	204.6	-26.7
SAP-4 c3	3.1	167.3	194.8	-27.6
SAP-3 c3	4.2	150.3	185.4	-35.1
SAP-2b c3	3.4	155.3	183.8	-28.5
SAP-1 c3	3.2	166.5	194.9	-28.4
SAP-2 c3	3.2	164.6	192.7	-28.1
ADS-6n c3	3.3	158.1	186.6	-28.5
ADS-7 c3	3.9	163.4	198.5	-35.1
ADPM c3	3.8	152.9	184.4	-31.6
ADPW c3	3.7	156.0	187.6	-31.6
ADPQ c3	3.5	157.5	187.5	-29.9
ADS-2 c3	2.6	145.0	165.0	-20.1
ADS-4 c3	4.7	144.4	182.6	-38.2
ADPR c3	4.6	147.0	185.5	-38.4
SAP-3 c4	3.5	162.3	193.4	-31.1
SAP-2b c4	2.9	142.5	164.4	-21.9
SAP-1 c4	3.6	163.2	195.3	-32.1
SAP-2 c4	3.6	165.1	197.5	-32.5
ADS-6n c4	3.2	139.1	163.2	-24.1
ADPW c4	2.8	150.9	173.7	-22.8
ADPQ c4	2.8	145.6	167.8	-22.3
ADS-4 c4	2.3	144.6	162.5	-17.9
ADPR c4	2.5	153.1	173.4	-20.3